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THE INFLUENCE ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT ON PERFORMANCE WITH ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR

ВПЛИВ ОРГАНІЗАЦІЙНОЇ КУЛЬТУРИ ТА ОРГАНІЗАЦІЙНИХ ЗОБОВ'ЯЗАНЬ НА ПРОДУКТИВНІСТЬ ЗА ДОПОМОГОЮ ОРГАНІЗАЦІЙНОЇ ГРОМАДЯНСЬКОЇ ПОВЕДІНКИ

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Агустіна Сарі Сітомпул, Сайфуддін, Кат Фітрі Ростіна, Роберт Туа Сірегар. Вплив організаційної культури та організаційних зобов'язань на продуктивність за допомогою організаційної громадянської поведінки. Оглядова стаття. Людські ресурси – це ресурси, які мають розум і почуття, бажання, навички, знання, заохочення та роботу, яку можна зробити для компанії. Це дослідження має на меті визначити, чи організаційна культура та організаційна відданість впливають на продуктивність співробітників через ОСВ як проміжну змінну в Секретаріаті DPRD Регентства Лабуханбату. Дослідження проводилося на 53 співробітниках за методикою насиченої вибірки. Використана техніка збору даних: первинні дані у формі анкет та вторинні дані, отримані шляхом вивчення документації. Техніка аналізу даних використовувала кількісні дані, які були оброблені за допомогою програми SPSS версії 25, а саме t-тест, тест Собеля та аналіз шляхів.

Ключові слова: організаційна культура, організаційна відданість, ОГП, продуктивність

Agustina Sari Sitompul, Syaifuddin, Cut Fitri Rostina, Robert Tua Siregar. *The Influence Organizational Culture and Organizational Commitment on Performance With Organizational Citizenship Behaviour. Review article.*

Human resources are resources that have reason and feelings, desires, skills, knowledge, encouragement and work that can be produced for the company. This study aims to determine whether organizational culture and organizational commitment affect employee performance through OCB as an intervening variable at the Labuhanbatu Regency DPRD Secretariat. The study was conducted on 53 employees using a saturated sampling technique. The data collection technique used was primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique used quantitative data which was processed using the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis.

Keywords: organizational culture, organizational commitment, OCB, performance

Every agency or organization always strives to improve the performance of employees with the expectation that the goal will be achieved as expected by an agency / organization. Employee performance has a very important role in an agency, if the agency has good human resources and has high performance, the goals of the agency can achieve the goals expected by the agency or organization.

Human resources are resources that have reason and feelings, desires, skills, knowledge, encouragement and work that can be produced for the company. All of these things affect the company to achieve its goals. Although technology, the development of information, capital and materials processed are sufficient, without human resources the company will find it difficult to achieve its goals.

One of the factors that affect the success rate of an organization is performance. According to Rismawati and Mattalata (2018: 3) employee performance is a condition that must be known and confirmed to certain parties to find out the level of achievement of an agency's results related to the vision carried out by a company or company and find out the positive and negative impacts of an operational policy.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

In this study, researchers used primary data and secondary data. According to Sanusi (2011:62), the types and sources of data are divided into two, namely:

1. Primary Data.

Primary data is data that is first recorded and collected by researchers. The primary data on this research was obtained through a questionnaire.

2. Secondary Data.

Secondary data is data that is already available and collected by other parties. Secondary data of this study were obtained through books and journals related to work facilities, compensation, performance and job satisfaction.

The data collection techniques used are:

1. List of questions (Questionnaire), by making a list of questions in the form of a questionnaire addressed to employees.

2. Documentation study, by collecting company / agency data related to research needs.

The main part

Testing the Classical Assumptions of Sub Model I. Multicollinearity Test Table for Sub Model I

Table 1. Coefficients^a

Type	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.253	11.362	0.286	
	Organizational Culture	0.979	0.202	0.569	
	Organizational Commitment	0.096	0.122	0.093	
	OCB	0.051	0.118	0.151	4.436

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source: authors' own elaboration

On the table, a statistical test t is obtained, as follows:

1) Variable OCB (Z), with a probability level of 0.005. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.005 > \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that states the OCB variable has a significant effect on Performance.

2) Organizational Culture Variable (X_1), with a probability level of 0.000. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.000 > \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that states organizational culture variables have a significant effect on Performance.

3) Organizational Commitment Variable (X_2), with a probability level of 0.033. Thus it can be inferred $P = 0.033 < \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that states the variable of organizational commitment has a significant effect on Performance.

Thus can be compiled the path analysis equation as follows:

$$Y = 0.569 X_1 + 0.093 X_2 + 0.151 Z.$$

The analysis equation model means:

1) Organizational Culture Variable (X_1) = 0.569. An organizational culture variable that is positively marked means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that any addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the buday a organizational variable will add a Performance variable value of 0.569 per one unit score.

2) Organizational Commitment Variable (X_2) = 0.093. A positively marked organizational commitment variable means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the organizational commitment variable will increase the value of the Performance variable by 0.093 per one unit score.

3) Variable OCB (Z) = 0.151. An OCB variable marked positive means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the OCB variable will increase the value of the Performance variable by 0.151 per one unit score.

Sobel test.

Mediation hypothesis testing can also be done with a procedure developed by Sobel and known as the sobel test. The Sobel test is carried out by testing the strength of indirect influence X to Y through Z, as follows:

$$Z = \frac{ab}{\sqrt{b^2 SE_a^2 + a^2 SE_b^2}} \tag{1}$$

where a – regression coefficient of an independent variable to the mediation variable,

b – regression coefficient of the mediation variable to the dependent variable

SE_a – standard error of estimation of the influence of independent variables on mediation variables

SE_b – standard error of estimation of the influence of mediation variables on dependent variables

The following are the results of the sobel test with organizational culture variables on performance through OCB.

$$t = \frac{0.100 \times 0.151}{\sqrt{(0.151^2 \times 0.242^2) + (0.100^2 \times 0.118^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.100 \times 0.151}{\sqrt{0.0013353178 + 0.00013924}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.0151}{0.0014745578}$$

$$t = 10.240.$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above getting a t value of 10.240, so that a calculated t value of $10.240 > t$ table 4.447 was obtained, it can be concluded that the OCB variable is able to mediate the relationship of the influence of organizational culture on performance.

The following hasil sobel test with variables of organizational commitment to performance through OCB.

$$t = \frac{0.174 \times 0.151}{\sqrt{(0.151^2 \times 0.146^2) + (0.174^2 \times 0.118^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.174 \times 0.151}{\sqrt{0.0004860261 + 0.000421563}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.026274}{0.0009075891}$$

$$t = 8.949.$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above getting a t value of 8.949, so that a calculated t value of $8.949 > t$ table 4.447 was obtained, it can be concluded that the OCB variable is able to mediate the relationship of the influence of organizational commitment on performance.

Path analysis.

The path diagram of the structure model II as follows:

Figure 1. Path Analysis

Source: authors' own elaboration

The results of the analysis show that the direct influence that Organizational Culture (X_1) exerts on Performance (Y) is 0.569. Meanwhile, the indirect influence of Organizational Culture (X_1) on performance (Y) through OCB (Z), which is $0.100 \times 0.093 = 0.0093$. Then the total effect given by the Organizational Culture variable (X_1) on Performance (Y) is a direct influence coupled with an indirect influence, which is $0.569 + 0.0093 = 0.58$. Based on the results of the calculations above, it can be seen that the direct influence value is 0.569 and indirect influence by 0.0093, which means that the value of direct influence is greater than that of the value of indirect influence. These results show that indirectly the Organizational Culture variable (X_1) through OCB (Z) has no significant influence on Performance (Y).

The results of the analysis show that the direct influence given by the Organizational Commitment (X_2) on Performance (Y) is 0.093. Meanwhile, the indirect influence of Organizational Commitment (X_2) on Kinerja (Y) through OCB (Z), which is $0.174 \times 0.151 = 0.026$. Then the total influence given by the variable Organizational

Commitment (X_2) on Performance (Y) is a direct influence coupled with an indirect influence, which is $0.093 + 0.026 = 0.119$. Based on the results of the above calculations, it can be known that the value of direct influence is 0.093 and indirect influence of 0.026, which means that the value of direct influence is greater than that of indirect influence. These results indicate that indirectly the Organizational Commitment variable (X_2) through OCB (Z) has no significant effect on Performance (Y).

Conclusions

a. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on OCB at the DPRD Secretariat of Labuhanbatu Regency. This means that this condition proves that organizational culture can improve OCB.

b. The organization's commitment has a positive and significant effect on the OCB at the Secretariat of the DPRD, Labuhanbatu Regency. This means that this condition proves that the higher the organization's commitment can affect OCB.

c. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on performance at the DPRD Secretariat of Labuhanbatu Regency. This means that this condition proves that organizational culture to employees can improve performance.

d. The organization's commitment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the DPRD Secretariat of Labuhanbatu Regency. This means that this condition proves that the higher the organization's commitment can improve employee performance.

e. OCB positively affects and significant against Performance at the Secretariat of the DPRD, Labuhanbatu Regency. This means that this condition proves that the better OCB employees can improve Employee Performance.

f. The influence of organizational culture on the performance of employees of the DPRD Secretariat of Labuhanbatu Regency will be smaller if it is carried out through OCB. The direct influence of organizational culture on employee performance is greater than the indirect influence of organizational culture on performance. It can be concluded that OCB is not able to mediate the influence of organizational culture on performance.

g. The effect of the organization's commitment on the productivity of Labuhanbatu District DPRD Secretariat workers will be less if it is done through OCB. The direct influence of organizational commitment on employee performance is greater than the indirect influence of organizational commitment to performance. This can be implied OCB is unable to mediate the effect of organizational commitment on performance.

Abstract

Human resources are resources that have reason and feelings, desires, skills, knowledge, encouragement and work that can be produced for the company. All of these things influence the company to achieve its goals. Even though technology, information development, capital and processed materials are sufficient, if without human resources the company will find it difficult to achieve its goals. This study aims to determine whether organizational culture and organizational commitment affect employee performance through OCB as an intervening variable at the Labuhanbatu Regency DPRD Secretariat.

The study was conducted on 53 employees using a saturated sampling technique. The data collection technique used was primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique used quantitative data which was processed using the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis.

The results obtained in this study show: 1) there is a significant influence between organizational culture on OCB, 2) there is a significant influence between organizational commitment variables on OCB, 3) there is a significant influence between organizational culture variables on performance, 4) there is a significant effect between commitment variables organization on performance, 5) there is a significant influence between OCB variables on performance, 6) OCB variables cannot affect organizational culture variables on performance, 7) OCB variables cannot affect organizational commitment variables on performance.

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